

Polarography of Xanthone

N. R. BANNERJEE*^a and R. CHAKRABORTY^b

^aChemistry Department, University of Delhi, Delhi-110 007

^bKarimganj College, Karimganj-788 710

Manuscript received 3 March 1994, revised 15 December 1995, accepted 9 May 1996

Day and Biggers¹ described polarographic reduction of xanthone over the pH range 1–13 and reported only one wave. They also found higher limiting current values in the pH range 5–9. They, however, did not propose any mechanism for the electrode process from these studies, and did not use any other electrochemical technique for such elucidation. The present investigation was, therefore, undertaken to verify the dc polarographic behaviour of xanthone and augment the results with cv, ac and Kalousek polarographic technique, millicoulometry, cpc and cpe studies and identification of the product by spectroscopy.

Results and Discussion

The dc polarograms of xanthone were recorded. The limiting current vs pH plots upto pH 4.7 show two equal waves. From pH 5.6 to 8.6, a single merged wave appears which separates into two unequal waves at pH 10.1. The latter wave separation results in a decay and a growth curve with increasing pH of solutions. At about pH 11.9, the first wave decays and the second wave grows to nearly half of their maximum values (in the second case, extrapolated value), reminiscent of polarographic pK value.

The $E_{1/2}$ vs pH plot exhibits a slope of -0.083 V per pH-unit for the first wave and -0.046 and -0.012 V per pH (over the two linear portions) for the second wave for acidic solutions (upto pH 4.7). From pH 5.6 to 8.6, the linear plot has a slope of -0.012 V; the slope then rises and falls till at a pH 11.75 it becomes -0.011 V per pH-unit; the slope of the plot for the second wave is pH-independent.

The limiting current is linearly proportional to concentration (0.1 to 0.9 mmol dm⁻³; pH 7.2) and to $h^{2/3}$ (controlled drop time 2 s) at pH 6.25 and to $h^{1/2}$ for natural droptime at pH 13.97 (for both the waves). In the latter case, the limiting currents are inversely proportional to the square-root of drop-times ($t^{-1/2} \propto h^{1/2}$) at the plateau potentials -1.5 and -1.7 V of the two waves respectively, indicating their diffusion-controlled nature.

To examine the effect of concentration (0.5 to 2.5 mmol dm⁻³) on the shapes of the polarograms, on their slopes and their half-wave potentials, polarograms were recorded at pH 7.2 (Table 1). The negative shift of half-wave potentials with increasing concentration and one-electron slope

for the two-electron process (proved later) indicates dimerisation of the ion-radical intermediate. Dimerisation constant was accordingly calculated² and found to be nearly constant (Table 1).

TABLE 1—CONCENTRATION EFFECT ON DC POLAROGRAMS OF XANTHONE

pH = 7.2 (Britton-Robinson buffer)					
Conc. mmol dm ⁻³	$E_{1/2}$ -V	Slope V	\bar{i}_d μA	I μA	$10^{-3}K_D$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹
0.5	1.225	0.052	1.652	0.560	13.730
1.0	1.238	0.054	3.525	1.300	13.800
1.5	1.240	0.059	5.325	2.050	13.600
2.0	1.244	0.063	7.100	2.800	12.938
2.5	1.247	0.070	8.950	3.580	12.000

Kalousek polarograms at pH's 4.7, 7.2 and 13.97 show that there is no anodic current for the former two pH-values, whereas more positive (at -0.8 V) anodic wave is seen in the polarogram for pH 13.97. Further cyclic voltammograms (HMDE) at pH's 3.5, 7.2 and 13.97 reveal no anodic peak for the acidic solutions, whereas the alkaline solution yields an anodic peak at $+0.6$ V more positive potential (at -0.81 V) than the cathodic first peak (-1.41 V), indicating tendency towards reversibility in alkaline solutions as seen in the case of Kalousek polarograms. In addition i_p vs $V^{1/2}$ (V = scan-rate) and i_p vs C plots were straight lines passing through the origin, indicating diffusion controlled nature of the electrode process. Also $i_p/V^{1/2}$ values are independent of the scan-rate indicating uncomplicated charge-transfer process. The value of an_a was found to be nearly unity from the relationship, $E_p = E_{p/2} = 0.048/an_a$. AC polarograms correspond more or less to the dc polarograms, two ac peaks upto pH 3.5, one ac peak between pH's 4.7 and 8.6 and two unequal ac peaks at pH 11.5. The base lines in the polarograms are above that of the supporting electrolyte, indicating no adsorption of xanthone or its reduction product.

Kinetic parameters^{3,4} of the electrode process have been calculated and the $K_{f,h}^0$ values at pH's 3.5 and 10.2 are 1.26×10^{-16} and 7.08×10^{-20} cm s⁻¹, again indicating irreversibility of the electrode process at these pH-values. Millicoulometry (0.2 mmol dm⁻³, pH 7.2) and cpc (2.026

*Present Address : 60, Vaishali, Pitampura, Delhi-110 034.

$\times 10^{-5}$ mol) at a stirred Hg pool cathode (tetramethylammonium phosphate buffer, pH 8.61) prove a consumption of two faradays per mole of xanthone. Constant potential electrolysis (20 cm^3 , 1.0 mmol dm^{-3} ; pH 7.2) was carried out till reduction was complete (2 h) and uv-spectrum was recorded. Spectra of the solution before electrolysis and that of a solution of xanthhydrol were also recorded, which proved that the two-electron reduction product was xanthhydrol.

Mechanism for the electrode process can be proposed from the following considerations. (i) In acidic solutions, there are two one-electron waves with one electron slopes upto pH 5.6. In the $E_{1/2}$ vs pH plot, slope for the first wave was -0.083 V and that for the second wave was -0.046 and -0.012 V per pH unit in this pH range. The mechanisms, therefore, are CECE in the former pH range (2.01 and 3.1) and CEEC in the latter range (3.5, 4.7 and 5.6) (Scheme 1). (ii) Between pH's 5.6 and 8.6, the $E_{1/2}$ value was nearly

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

Scheme 3

independent of pH. Hence prior protonation was not probable here and an EECC mechanism should hold for the purpose (Scheme 2). A competitive dimerisation of ion-radical formed on one-electron uptake also occurs in this pH-range. (iii) Above pH 8.6, where a second wave appears and grows with increasing pH at the expense of the first, an EECC mechanism can be proposed with the addition that the intermediate radical anion can also combine with a cation and this stabilised complex ion is reduced to the final product at more negative potentials. The increasing height of the second wave with increasing pH is due to increasing concentration of the tetramethylammonium ion in the solution (Scheme 3).

Experimental

A Bruker E310 polarograph in conjunction with Hewlett-Packard 7050A X-Y recorder was used. Capillary characteristics were: $m = 1.293 \text{ mg s}^{-1}$ and $t = 4.1 \text{ s}$ at 40 cm height of Hg reservoir and controlled droptime of 2.5 s was used. The pH-values of 1 : 1 aqueous ethanolic universal buffered xanthone solutions were checked with an Elico LI 120 pH meter (accuracy ± 0.01 pH-unit). For constant potential coulometry (cpc), a digital coulometer (model 640, The Electroynthesis Co., U.S.A.) was used. For constant potential electrolysis (cpe), a locally made 5V, 3A potentiostat-galvanostat was used to apply the required potential (vs sce) and the extent of electrolysis was monitored by recording polarograms with a dme already fitted into the electrolytic H-type cell.

The test solutions contained 2.5 cm^3 of ethanolic (5.0 mmol dm^{-3}) xanthone solution, 12.5 cm^3 of aqueous acetate-phosphate-borate universal buffer ($0.026 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ each), 10 cm^3 of additional ethanol and calculated amount of tetramethylammonium bromide made up to 25 cm^3 with distilled water, making the final solution 0.5 mmol dm^{-3} in xanthone, 0.04 mol dm^{-3} in buffer, 0.1 mol dm^{-3} in ionic strength and 50% (v/v) in ethanol. For cpc and cpe, the concentrations of depolariser and buffer are given at appropriate places.

References

1. R. A. DAY, JR. and R. E. BIGGERS, *J Am Chem Soc*, 1953, 75, 738.
2. J. HEYROVSKY and J. KUTA, "Principle of Polarography", Academic, New York, 1965, p. 186.
3. J. WEBER and J. KOUTECKY, *Collect Czech Chem Commun*, 1955, 20, 980.
4. J. KOUTECKY and J. CIZLIK, *Collect Czech Chem Commun*, 1956, 21, 836.